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Legume Hub Members' Newsletter 1

Establishing the Legume Hub Community/Association, 23 August 2021

Welcome to the first newsletter of the Legume Hub Association. The purpose is to keep you informed about the development of your Legume Hub and to support interaction between members and with those who manage and administer the Hub for you.

The Legume Hub is a mutually-owned self-publishing platform for all interested in the development of legume production and use in Europe. We want to bring that ambition to life. We now have 56 members from various backgrounds (see the attached list). The Hub now hosts output from three EU projects. We have recently received enquiries for hosting publications from German operational groups. The overall picture is one of steady growth. A more detailed analysis of the contents already available on the Hub is attached. A step-by-step video for creating a pdf upload can be found [here](#).

The Hub is currently run during this founding phase by the members of the executive committee of the Legumes Translated project. We now want to turn our attention to establishing a permanent governance arrangement in line with the statutes so that the governance is properly in the hands of its members extending beyond the life of Legume Translated. We are therefore planning the first meeting of the members to take place in September. All members will be invited. For those who do not have a public profile yet and are interested in one, [here](#) is a supporting video.

We do not expect this meeting (probably using Zoom) to take long. Potential agenda items are:

- Approval of the statutes.
- Election of the chairman of the association and its board.

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- Election of members of the board.
- Arrangements for the editorial board.

Your suggestions on agenda items and any other matters are welcome, by way of reply to the email or by contacting me directly (donal@murphy-bokern.com).

Donal Murphy-Bokern

Interim Chairman

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